

Supplemental Table S1. A summary of the species included in this study along with details regarding the RNA-seq dataset including BioProject ID, library layout, number of unique samples used in this study, source of reference transcriptome, and references to the original study whenever available. File also available at <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.9w0vt4bmk>

Supplemental Figure S1. A) Distribution of relative specificity or uniformity of Inr and Y patch containing promoters for all fifteen species. B) Distribution of relative specificity or uniformity of TATA and Coreless containing promoters in *Zea mays* using a generic TATA motif from Jores et al. and a maize specific TATA motif from Mejía-Guerra et al.. Higher Coefficient of Variation (CV) rankings indicate more specificity, while lower CV rankings indicate more uniformity. A random subsampling of forty percent of promoters from each species are shown here. A further random subsampling of twenty percent of the promoters were used in the Random set as a control. Colors correspond to phylogeny shown in Figure 1A.

Supplemental Figure S2. Distribution of coefficient of variation for transcripts in *Arabidopsis* that contained only a single read (removed), and the rest of the transcripts (kept). “n” above the beeswarm plot represents the number of transcripts in each group.

	Random		Stable		Unstable	
	Target Orthologs	<i>Arabidopsis</i> Transcripts	Target Orthologs	<i>Arabidopsis</i> Transcripts	Target Orthologs	<i>Arabidopsis</i> Transcripts
Highest expressing target transcript only	22,339	1,197	25,427	1,323	14,350	934
Single ortholog in target transcriptome	4,066	984	6,505	1,224	2,149	682
Changed expression pattern in at least 2 target species	NA	NA	189	27	345	58
High confidence candidates	NA	NA	17	3	21	4

Supplemental Table S2. Number of *Arabidopsis* transcripts and target orthologs after each filtering step. The random set of genes were not used in analysis involving changes in expression patterns from *Arabidopsis*, and the counts were left as NA.

Supplemental Figure S3. Regions searched for the various core promoter octamers. The regions were defined in Yamamoto et al. 2009.

Supplemental Table S3. Summary of the core promoter scanning results. The transcripts are grouped by orthologous gene groups. “Change” denotes whether there is a change in expression pattern compared to the *Arabidopsis* transcript (*Arabidopsis* is always unchanged. i.e. “Unstable_to_Unstable” or “Stable_to_Stable”), and those that changed expression compared to *Arabidopsis* are highlighted orange. CV_PR and Gmean_PR are the percent ranking of CV and geometric mean within the species, respectively. At_transcript_id is the column used to define each orthologous gene group and it is the *Arabidopsis* transcript that the gene group is related to. TATA, Inr, BREu, BREd, Ypatch, and TCT are core promoter elements screened using “Motif Scan” method, and the columns are highlighted in yellow. The numbers are relative motif scores and scores above 0.85 are considered positive. TATA_result, Ypatch_result, Ypatch_resultUTR, Inr_result, GA_result, GA_resultUTR, CA_result are core promoter elements screened using “Octamer Scan” method, and the columns are highlighted green. Details regarding the two scanning methods can be found in the methods section. The presence of a core promoter element for either method is highlighted in green. Gene symbol (Symbol) and Description are from TAIR. File also available at <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.9w0vt4bmk>

Supplementary Data S1. MultiQC outputs for the RNA-seq analysis pipeline. The MultiQC output for RNA-seq datasets from each species is stored as html files, and each file provides a visual summary of results from FastQC, Trimmomatic, and Kallisto. File available at <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.9w0vt4bmk>